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Motivation

SCAN
ME

With >6.3 billion tons of plastic waste already discarded—and projections suggesting that, without intervention, the average person will generate plastic waste equivalent to the weight of a car by 2050 [2]—the need for innovative solutions is urgent. We study the process of pyrolysis, which mainly involves reaction and separation units. With established theoretical foundation, we use modeling, simulation, parameter estimation, and optimization to advance operation of pyrolysis plant for sustainable plastic management.

Pyrolysis of LDPE

Simplified reaction scheme:

Plant design: Oxygen-free endothermic reaction

Figure: Schematic diagram of a pyrolysis plant.

Reaction Mechanism of LDPE Pyrolysis

Assumption: LDPE chains break via a random-scission mechanism.

Kinetic model: A single first-order random-scission model [3]

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = Ae^{-\frac{E}{RT}}(1-x)$$

x – extent of bond cleavage in the polymer chain, nonlinear relationship w.r.t. the conversion α , $\alpha = f(x)$

Model Validation and Parameter Estimation

Conclusions

We constructed and successfully validated the process simulation. The developed model provides a reasonably precise description of plastics pyrolysis. We also showcased an optimization framework and optimized production parameters. Future work involves modeling a pyrolysis plant in gPROMS Process Builder.

[1] F. S. Atalay. Kinetics of the esterification reaction between ethanol and acetic acid. *Developments in Chemical Engineering and Mineral Processing*, 2(2-3):181–184, 1994.

[2] Roland Geyer, Jenna R. Jambeck, and Kara Lavender Law. Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Science Advances*, 3(7):e1700782, 2017.

[3] Dongting Zhao, Xianhua Wang, James B. Miller, and George W. Huber. The chemistry and kinetics of polyethylene pyrolysis: A process to produce fuels and chemicals. *ChemSusChem*, 13(7):1764–1774, 2020.

Reactor-Separation Model Design

Used software: gPROMS Process Builder PML library

Model reaction: Esterification [1]

Assumptions:

- reactor: isothermal, single phase, ideally mixed
- reaction: only forward reaction with the following kinetics

$$\frac{dc_D}{dt} = 0.496e^{-310/T} c_A^{0.5} c_B^{0.5}$$

Distillation model: gPROMS distillation column model

Reaction-Separation Simulation

Optimization

gPROMS optimization setup:

Steady-state optimization problem: $\min f(x)$ s.t. $x \in \mathbb{X} := \{x | g(x) \leq 0\}$

Distillation optimization:

Objective $f(x)$	max distillate mass fraction
Variable x	reflux ratio
Constraints \mathbb{X}	distillate flowrate ≥ 5 kg/h

Results: converged

Objective value	0.858568
Variable value	5.80671
Constraint value	5.01049 kg/h